

DRAFT

Satellite Remote Sensing in a Rational Planning Process for Water Resources Planning

The Landsat Thematic Mapper image above was taken June 2006 of portions of the Uncompahgre and Lower Gunnison Valleys in the Upper Colorado River Basin. The image on the left is a composite color image while the right shows 24-hour evapotranspiration developed using an energy balance model (red: low to purple: high evapotranspiration rates) (source: USGS, 2014. Monitoring Consumptive Water Use for Global Crop Production. [online] Available at:<https://www.fort.usgs.gov/sites/case-studies/monitoring-consumptive-water-use-global-crop-production> > [Accessed: November 2, 2015])

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1.0 Introduction and Research Question

This paper was prepared in partial fulfillment of the graduate course Water Resources Planning (EN.575.731 (81), Whiting School of Engineering, Johns Hopkins University.

The primary research question underlying this paper is:

- *Is satellite remote sensing useful in a rational planning process for water resources planning?*

Seemingly, the answer is yes; however, there are practical issues that need to be addressed (secondary research questions), such as: 1) Where might satellite remote sensing fit into a rational planning process? 2) If barriers to adoption of satellite remote sensing techniques exist, what are they?

Based on an extensive literature review, this paper first address the secondary research questions, and then answers the primary research question. Also, importantly, since knowledge of the range of possible applications of remote sensing is required before satellite remote sensing can be considered for use in a rational planning process, carefully selected case studies summaries are presented to illustrate the diversity of application. After reading this paper it is my hope that you will consider applying satellite remote sensing to some of your water resources planning projects.

The remaining sections guide the reader through this research and findings:

- Section 2.0** What is Satellite Remote Sensing?
- Section 3.0** Examples of Satellite Remote Sensing use in Water Resources Planning
- Section 4.0** Satellite Remote Sensing in a Rational Planning Process
- Section 5.0** Barriers to Adoption of Satellite Remote Sensing
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2.0 What is Satellite Remote Sensing?

Satellite remote sensing (RS) is *the science and technology of collecting earth resource information from space using satellites*¹. Operating at the frontiers of human inquiry, satellite RS is well established and continues to evolve with advances in satellite technology and innovative sensor development and/or new analysis methodologies^{2,3}. RS satellites are equipped with a variety of information gathering sensors and cameras to remotely collect a range of specialized photographs and/or data. Because satellite RS

¹ Lillesand, T., Kiefer, R.W. & Chipman, J., 2014. Remote sensing and image interpretation, John Wiley & Sons.

² Belward, A.S. & Skøien, J.O., 2015. Who launched what, when and why; trends in global land-cover observation capacity from civilian earth observation satellites, *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, vol. 103, pp. 115-128.

³ Sabins Jr, F.F., 1978. Remote sensing. *Freeman: San Francisco*. 426 p.

systems operate from space, image and data can be accurately gathered over large geographic areas and time⁴. Images and data are typically stored on a computer server and accessible via an Internet connection. In addition to water resources planning, satellite RS is used in archeology, ecology/biodiversity, climate studies/climate change, medical epidemiology, and many more fields^{5,6,7,8,9}. Increasingly satellite images and data products, especially those from official government sources, are available to researchers and the public at no cost. Example images obtainable from Landsat, a 40-year satellite remote sensing program of the US Department of the Interior¹⁰, are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 below.

Figure 1 – Example 1 Remote Sensing Image Time Series (Aral Sea Destruction). The Aral Sea, located in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan in central Asia, was once one of the largest inland bodies in the world. Over the last 30 years, the Sea has diminished in capacity dramatically, as shown in these images captured by the Landsat series of satellites. A major factor causing the shrinkage is upstream water use for crop irrigation. (Image and Description Source: Landsat program, US Department of the Interior. Image Available at:< <http://landsat.usgs.gov//index.php>>)

⁴ Schaeffer, B.A., Schaeffer, K.G., Keith, D., Lunetta, R.S., Conmy, R. & Gould, R.W., 2013. Barriers to adopting satellite remote sensing for water quality management, *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 34, no. 21, pp. 7534-7544.

⁵ Lasaponara, R. & Masini, N., 2012. Satellite remote sensing: A new tool for archaeology, Springer Science & Business Media.

⁶ Lobitz, B., Beck, L., Huq, A., Wood, B., Fuchs, G., Faruque, A.S. & Colwell, R., 2000. Climate and infectious disease: use of remote sensing for detection of *Vibrio cholerae* by indirect measurement, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 97, no. 4, pp. 1438-1443.

⁷ DeFries, R., Achard, F., Brown, S., Herold, M., Murdiyarso, D., Schlamadinger, B. & de Souza, C., 2007. Earth observations for estimating greenhouse gas emissions from deforestation in developing countries, *Environmental Science & Policy*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 385-394.

⁸ Turner, W., Rondinini, C., Pettorelli, N., Mora, B., Leidner, A., Szantoi, Z., Buchanan, G., Dech, S., Dwyer, J. & Herold, M., 2015. Free and open-access satellite data are key to biodiversity conservation, *Biological Conservation*, vol. 182, pp. 173-176.

⁹ Field, C.B., Randerson, J.T. & Malmström, C.M., 1995. Global net primary production: combining ecology and remote sensing, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 74-88.

¹⁰ US Department of the Interior, 2015. Landsat. [online] Available at:< http://landsat.usgs.gov//Landsat_Stories.php> [Accessed: 30 October 2015]

Figure 2 – Example 2 Remote Sensing Enhanced Image (Estuary, Western Australia). Landsat Image, Western Australia. Details: This image is a portion of the first Landsat 8 scene acquired May 12, 2013 (Path 107, Rows 70-71) in Western Australia. Geoscience Australia, a Landsat International Cooperator and a Landsat Science Team Member, produced this enhanced image. The resulting image displays impressive sediment and nutrient patterns in the tropical estuary area, and the complex patterns and conditions in the vegetated areas. *(Image and Description Source: Landsat program, US Department of the Interior. Image Available at: <<http://landsat.usgs.gov//index.php>>)*

3.0 Examples of Satellite Remote Sensing use in Water Resources Planning

To illustrate some of the applications of satellite RS to water resources, brief summaries of carefully selected case studies are presented below. For additional information, please consult the references provided. In addition, **Table 1** provides a summary for each case study by resource type, lists imaging sensors used, and provides a website link to each satellite RS program.

Case Studies:

- **Water Supply Availability from Snow Melt (Argentina)¹¹**
To aid water supply planners in producing accurate seasonal water availability forecasts satellite remote sensing was used to understand relationships between snow accumulation and water availability. This work produced an improved discharge forecasting method for seasonal agricultural irrigation.
- **Water Supply Demand Forecasting and Agriculture Land Protection (Egypt)¹²**
Water supply demand forecasting and agricultural land protection in the Nile Delta, Egypt is a complex process requiring data on landuse changes, land degradation and fragmentation, and agricultural use. Use of satellite RS allowed planners to plan agricultural landuse expansion and refine water supply demand forecasting.
- **Aquifer Depletion Evaluation (California)^{13,14}**
This groundbreaking program documented unsustainable changes in aquifer storage using gravity measurements from satellite RS. Overreliance on groundwater, generally unregulated and not monitored, for use in agricultural irrigation, has severely depleted the regional aquifer in California's Central Valley. The Central Valley of California is the most productive agricultural regions in the USA¹⁵.
- **Flooding Hazard Modeling and Forecasting¹⁶**
Because of satellite RS's wide and detailed geographic coverage, a greater variety of landuse types and corresponding runoff coefficients were incorporated in the flood modeling and forecasting for this project. Using satellite RS compared to conventional methods of flood forecasting, this project documented significant improvement in predictions of peak flood flow.

For more case studies involving water resources and use of the Landsat program, see: <
<https://www.fort.usgs.gov/sites/case-studies/29095/28481>. See also the Landsat studies ebook, available at: http://landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/?page_id=6724 and <http://naldc.nal.usda.gov/download/59934/PDF>>.

¹¹ Delbart, N., Dunesme, S., Lavie, E., Madelin, M. & Goma, R., 2015. Remote sensing of Andean mountain snow cover to forecast water discharge of Cuyo rivers, *Journal of Alpine Research | Revue de géographie alpine*, no. 103-2.

¹² Elhag, M., Psilovikos, A. & Sakellariou-Makrantonaki, M., 2013. Land use changes and its impacts on water resources in Nile Delta region using remote sensing techniques, *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 1189-1204.

¹³ Famiglietti, J., Lo, M., Ho, S., Bethune, J., Anderson, K., Syed, T., Swenson, S., de Linage, C. & Rodell, M., 2011. Satellites measure recent rates of groundwater depletion in California's Central Valley, *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol. 38, no. 3.

¹⁴ Scanlon, B.R., Faunt, C.C., Longuevergne, L., Reedy, R.C., Alley, W.M., McGuire, V.L. & McMahon, P.B., 2012. Groundwater depletion and sustainability of irrigation in the US High Plains and Central Valley, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 109, no. 24, pp. 9320-9325.

¹⁵ Faunt, C.C., 2009. Groundwater availability of the central valley aquifer, California, *River Research and Applications*, vol. 26, pp. 730-741.

¹⁶ Tao, T. & Kouwen, N., 1989. Remote sensing and fully distributed modeling for flood forecasting, *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 115, no. 6, pp. 809-823.

Table 1 – Water Resources Planning using Satellite Remote Sensing

Ref. Page No.	Case Study Title / Environmental Resource	Sensing Technology	Satellite Program	Program Reference(s)
6	Flood Hazard Modeling and Forecasting / Surface water	1) MSS ¹	1) Landsat Missions (multiple)	1) https://landsat.usgs.gov
6	Water Supply Availability from Snowmelt / Surface water	1) MODIS ²	1) Terra and Aqua satellites (originally the EOS program)	1) http://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov
6	Aquifer Depletion Investigation / Groundwater	1) Gravimetric	1) GRACE (Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment)	1) http://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/Features/GRACE/
4,5	Example 1 – Aral Sea / Surface water (Lake) Example 2 – Estuary, Western Australia / Tidal wetland	1) MSS, TM ³ , ETM+ ⁴ 2) OLI ⁵	1) Landsat Missions 2, 5, 7 2) Landsat Mission 8	1) https://landsat.usgs.gov 2) https://landsat.usgs.gov
6	Water Supply Demand Forecasting / Agricultural water use	1) TM, ETM+	1) Landsat Missions 5, 7	1) https://landsat.usgs.gov

¹ multispectral scanner

² moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer

³ thematic mapper

⁴ multispectral scanning radiometer

⁵ operational land imager

4.0 Satellite Remote Sensing in a Rational Planning Process

Many of the problems encountered in water resources occur over long periods of time, progressively worsening in severity and changing in nature and/or geographic extent. For these kinds of problems, if used early in a rational planning process (RPP), application of satellite RS techniques can benefit a planning process. Since the collection of fundamental data using conventional means, e.g., monitoring wells, field surveys, and so on, over large geographic areas and for extended periods of time is expensive, time consuming, and in some cases impractical, satellite RS techniques can bring substantial cost savings, create new efficiencies, and improve an RPP¹⁷. In addition, as described in **Section 2.0**, images and data collected by satellite RS are capable of providing new insight and broader contextual information for large geographic areas and over long periods of time.

Typical problems in water resources suitable for investigation by satellite RS:

- Riparian erosion
- Wetland destruction
- Aquifer over-pumping
- Large scale flooding
- Development encroachment on aquifer protection areas
- Crop water consumption for demand planning
- Changing snow/ice melt schedule, reducing surface water supply

The initial steps in an RPP are the most important to clearly define the problem, and to guide the subsequent planning steps¹⁸. The typical steps of an RPP are listed below¹⁹:

1. **Identify the problem**
2. **Collect data and perform data analysis**
3. Develop goals and objectives
4. Clarify and diagnose problems or issues
5. Identify alternative solutions
6. Analyze alternatives
7. Evaluation and recommendation
8. Develop implementation program
9. *Perform surveillance and monitoring*

Applying satellite RS in the early steps, specifically, RPP steps 1 and 2 (**bold face** type above) of an RPP will produce the most benefit. In addition, because of the powerful

¹⁷ Tao, T. & Kouwen, N., 1989. Remote sensing and fully distributed modeling for flood forecasting, *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 115, no. 6, pp. 809-823.

¹⁸ *Ibid*

¹⁹ Dzurik, A.A., 2003. Water resources planning, Rowman & Littlefield. p. 85

capability of satellite RS techniques to quickly detect changes on the earth's surface, post-project implementation of surveillance and monitoring (Step 9) can also benefit from the use of satellite RS techniques.

5.0 Barriers to Adoption of Satellite Remote Sensing

A joint research effort by the US EPA and US Naval Research Laboratory studied the barriers to adoption of satellite RS techniques²⁰. Although the investigators focused specifically on the use of satellite RS applied to water quality problems, their findings are nonetheless interesting and relevant to understanding the broader water resources context of this paper. This section is based in part on the joint research paper.

Perceived barriers to adoption²¹:

- **Cost** – There was a misperception among the majority of interviewees that satellite RS images and data are available only for purchase.

Note: Most government sponsored satellite RS programs make images, data, and technical program information available to researchers and the public at no charge.

The initial (*start up*) costs of computers and peripherals, image processing and GIS software, and technical training for staff were also considered.

Note: Initial costs should be compared to the cost of a conventional approach to investigation and data gathering, e.g., sampling and field surveys, to determine if project cost savings and/or improved cost-benefit may be created given the specific details of a project.

- **Accuracy** – Interviewees expressed concern about representativeness, accuracy, and error estimates for satellite RS products, specifically for water quality applications.

Note: These responses are understandable since federal and state laws specify maximum allowable concentrations of constituents, and often the specific laboratory analytical method by which the concentration must be determined – with no mention in the legal code of the acceptability and/or standing of remote

²⁰ Schaeffer, B.A., Schaeffer, K.G., Keith, D., Lunetta, R.S., Conmy, R. & Gould, R.W., 2013. Barriers to adopting satellite remote sensing for water quality management, *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 34, no. 21, pp. 7534-7544.

²¹ *Ibid.* In the study, a systematic written survey questionnaire was distributed to a group (~15 individuals) of US EPA personnel. The group consisted of a mix project managers and technical personnel, some with no knowledge of satellite RS, others with knowledge and experience. As such, these unique findings represent the perceptions of the personnel interviewed.

sensing gathered information. In the case of water quality parameters, how does one reconcile the conflict? One solution is to augment satellite RS derived water quality data with conventional sampling and laboratory analysis, as needed. Another is to reference similar, peer-reviewed case studies and/or successful government remote sensing projects. Particularly for sensitive water resource projects, i.e., involving water quality and/or wetlands, pre-project agreement with the regulatory agency responsible for a project area about the possible use of satellite remote sensing, if applicable, is highly recommended.

- **Data Continuity** – There was general agreement among interviewees that satellite RS techniques can provide long term coverage of a project area. Some concern was expressed that a particular satellite RS program could shut down due to funding or other change.

Note: There are numerous examples in the literature where one satellite was retired and another one was used to continue the data gathering²². So the concern does not seem to be a major problem for the future of satellite RS use.

- **Program Support** – Executive-level sponsorship/support of the use of a satellite RS was seen by many of the interviewees as crucial to the sustainable adoption and program success. Without executive support, it was reported, interest in using the technology would quickly fade as inadequate budgets and conventional ways of completing planning projects were encountered.

6.0 Findings

Satellite RS is an established science and technology, and is in wide use in the water resources sector, both for new data collection and change monitoring. Satellite RS techniques allow for data collection and monitoring of large geographic areas, including remote and poorly accessible areas, and over long periods of time - in extreme examples, for decades. Depending on the goals, locations, and time period of a planning project, improved cost-benefit as well as overall project cost reduction may be achievable when satellite RS techniques are used in lieu of conventional sampling and field surveys.

Few, if any, case studies have been published in the scientific literature documenting satellite RS techniques specifically used in a rational planning process. However, of the large number of technical case studies reviewed for this paper, most were used to support some form of abbreviated planning and decision-making process.

Based on these research findings, I conclude that satellite RS can be useful in a rational planning process, and should be seriously evaluated for use.

²² For example, successive satellite missions, i.e., Landsat 2, 5, and 7, were used over a 30-year period to document changes in the extent of the Aral Sea. For more detail, refer to < <http://landsat.usgs.gov/index.php> >.